

NOAA's Hurricane Hunters Ready to Face the 2021 Hurricane Season

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Originally published by The Aviationist

<https://theaviationist.com/2021/05/21/noaa-aoc-lakeland>

Published: May 21, 2021

ASX Research Journal and Database

(Online Journal – ISSN Pending)

Place of Publication: Tampa, FL

Publisher: ASXResearch.org

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The author reports no conflicts of interest.

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Abstract

This article provides an in-depth look at the U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA) Aircraft Operations Center (AOC) in Lakeland, Florida, ahead of the 2021 Atlantic hurricane season. Through first-hand observations and direct interaction with NOAA personnel, it explores the mission, aircraft, and operational capabilities of the agency's Hurricane Hunter program. Key insights include historical context regarding the AOC's relocation from MacDill AFB, the unique specifications of NOAA's WP-3D Orion and Gulfstream IV-SP platforms, and the agency's crucial role in atmospheric and oceanic data collection. The piece combines journalistic clarity with technical accuracy, offering a valuable public and academic resource on hurricane forecasting, airborne data acquisition, and scientific readiness. All photographs and imagery included are original works by the author and document NOAA aircraft, personnel, and facilities in operational environments.

Keywords: NOAA, hurricane hunters, wp-3d orion, atmospheric research

NOAA's Hurricane Hunters Ready to Face the 2021 Hurricane Season

On May 1, 2017, the United States' National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) moved its Aircraft Operations Center (AOC) to a brand new 156,043 square foot facility at the Lakeland Linder International Airport (LAL) in Lakeland, Florida. They moved from their 99,000 square foot facility at MacDill AFB (MCF) in Tampa, Florida. The move to their new home provided NOAA with mission-specific facilities and a 37% increase in usable operations area (NOAA, 2017).

The NOAA AOC move was necessary because MacDill AFB, primarily a KC-135R tanker base, needed additional room for an incoming KC-135R squadron, the 50th Air Refueling Squadron (the Big 5-0, as MacDill's Deputy Chief of Public Affairs Terry Montrose told me), a squadron with roots dating back to WWII. The Big 5-0 took possession of NOAA's former space on October 2, 2017, and added 250+ personnel to the roster at MacDill AFB (Montrose, personal communication, 2021).

In review, NOAA's move from MacDill AFB to Lakeland Linder International Airport turned out to be a huge win-win for both NOAA and MacDill AFB.

Fast-forward to May 2021, about a month before the official start of the 2021 hurricane season. That's a fast-forward that jumped a significant global event: COVID-19. In speaking with some of the team members at NOAA during my visit, I was privileged to receive a wealth of information and resources for this article. To cover the effects of COVID-19 on NOAA's AOC mission would require a separate, in-depth article. What they did convey without hesitation, and with total certainty, was that NOAA and its dedicated, ultra-capable people remained steadfast in their global mission, including hurricane research (NOAA, 2020a).

During the 2020 season, NOAA's Aircraft Operations Center supported this critical data collection with 31 flights and 219.2 flight hours on the NOAA Gulfstream IV-SP, and 55 flights and 459 flight hours on NOAA's two WP-3D Orion Hurricane Hunters. Crews aboard the Hurricane Hunters released 1,772 dropsondes and 28 airborne expendable bathythermographs (AXBTs), feeding vital data on atmospheric and oceanic conditions into forecast models. NOAA Corps pilots and navigators, along with NOAA engineers, technicians, and meteorologists, crossed through the eye of a hurricane over 102 times aboard WP-3D Orions during flights through Hurricanes Hanna, Isaias, Laura, Paulette, Sally, Teddy, Delta, Zeta, and Eta (NOAA, 2020b).

NOAA currently operates four manned aircraft types. These include two Beechcraft King Air 350CERs (N67RF and N68RF), used primarily for coastal mapping, snow and soil moisture surveys, and emergency response missions. Four De Havilland DHC-6-300 Twin Otters (N46RF, N48RF, N56RF, and N57RF) are deployed for snow measurement research and right whale conservation. One Gulfstream IV-SP ("Gonzo," N49RF) is used for upper-atmosphere hurricane research and forecasting. Two Lockheed WP-3D Orions ("Kermit" and "Miss Piggy," N42RF and N43RF) remain NOAA's most iconic hurricane hunting platforms, uniquely built for the agency and first flown in 1975 (OMAO, 2021).

These aircraft are equipped with an array of scientific tools: spectrographic lasers, radar systems, UAVs, and dropsondes - all integral to storm tracking and analysis. After each mission, the aircraft are marked with "victory" icons representing the storms they've flown through. The crew told me that these markings not only serve as proud symbols but also underscore NOAA's global reach (Clark, 2021).

Our visit to NOAA's AOC concluded with a meeting with base commander Cmdr. Christian Sloan. Despite the intensity of his role, Cmdr. Sloan came across as approachable, grounded, and deeply knowledgeable - a reflection of the entire team. The professionalism, pride, and precision evident in the hangars, offices, and aircraft mirrored my prior experiences with elite aviation units like the U.S. Navy's Blue Angels. It was clear: excellence at NOAA begins at the top.

This article is the first in a planned series of NOAA features. Among upcoming stories: the account of a WP-3D losing an engine in a Category-5 storm and flying as low as 100 feet AGL. That story was shared with us by NOAA Flight Meteorologist Jack Parrish and Science Branch Chief Paul T. Flaherty - both legends in their field.

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Photographic Supplement: NOAA Hurricane Hunters

Figure 1. NOAA43 approaches NOAA's Air Operations Center (AOC) after a hurricane hunting training sortie. Inset images show aircraft markings, facility entrance, and drosonde launch ports. All Images © ASXResearch.org.

Figure 2. The main entrance to NOAA's AOC facility in Lakeland, Florida.

Figure 3. The main lobby at NOAA's AOC facility in Lakeland, Florida, which leads to their offices, workshops, and hangars.

Figure 4. NOAA's Beechcraft King Air 350CER. I don't think I've ever seen a more beautiful King Air! The King Airs primarily support coastal mapping, snow and soil moisture surveys, and emergency response missions.

Figure 5. This photo well illustrates the effort put into maintaining NOAA's facility and aircraft. This was NOT a staged photo. We just walked up on these happy guys working their tails-off making Twin Otter NOAA57 ready for her upcoming trip to Alaska for snow.

Figure 6. NOAA43 approaches NOAA's Air Operations Center after a hurricane hunting training sortie.

Figure 7. NOAA43 is seen taxiing with Lakeland's new tower in the background. Look closely and you can see that these images were taken on one of central Florida's 90°+ days.

Figure 8. Direct head-on view of NOAA42 illustrating the massive propellers of Lockheed's WP-3D Orion. Lockheed originally came up with this design hoping the giant props would generate extra lift, which they do.

Figure 9. This is an interesting photograph because it encompasses a lot of the Lakeland Linder International Airport: We see NOAA's two WP-3Ds (Kermit in the foreground and Miss Piggy taxiing), we see a general aviation Cessna departing runway 27 to the west, and to the very left of the photo you can see the beginning of the Amazon Prime airport facility. Amazon Prime's presence is BIG at LAL, and it will be the feature of an upcoming article.

Figure 10. A dropsonde is an expendable weather reconnaissance device created by the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). These are the ports through which NOAA's dropsondes fall.

Figure 11. The cockpit of WP-3D “Kermit”. We can tell this because of the small Kermit doll hanging over the instrument panel. Miss Piggy has one of her, hanging there too. I’ve been told by the pilots that they can tell how strong a storm is by how much the dolls bounce. Technology.

Figure 12. After every storm intercept, NOAA’s aircraft are adorned with a “victory mark” with the name of the storm in it. Also, the markings plainly illustrate that NOAA’s scope is global.

Figure 13. NOAA AOC's on facility, state-of-the-art conference and presentation room.

Figure 14. Quartering view of NOAA42, "Kermit the Frog". Kermit currently differs from Miss Piggy in that it has a weather probe protruding from it nose radome AND port wing. Miss Piggy only has the probe on her port wing.

Figure 15. Miss Piggy artwork created by the author.